

ISic3525

I.Sicily inscription 3525

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido, recinto H, sep.56

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3551

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. P(ublio) · Avillio · P(ubli) · f(ilio) ·
2. Pudentino
3. vixit · a(nnis) · XI · m(ensibus) · VI
4. P(ublius) · Avillius · Zosi
5. mus · P(ublio) Avillio Pudenti ·
6. Fl(aviae) · Meviae · Merope · fec(it) ·

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 with photograph

Translation (en)

To Publius Avillius Pudentinus, son of Publius, who died at 11 years, 6 months. Publius Avillius Zosimus set this up for Publius Avillius Pudens and Flavia Mevia Merope.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284776

EDR 033618

EDCS 14805801

PHI 313647

Bibliography

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Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 174-175 fig.40

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